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An Analysis of the Factors Affecting the Higher Education Demands of Nigerian Students in TRNC Universities: The Case of Girne American University[☆]

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ABSTRACT

The need and desire for higher education are increasing and the number of international students going abroad continues to be in high demand. In addition, the competition in higher education in the world has gained a global dimension by exceeding the borders of countries. However, some countries are preferred by international students as places of study. At this point, the TRNC is seen as a country that attracts students, and most of the students coming to the TRNC come from African countries, the Middle East, Central Asia, and Turkey. According to Tomlinson, (2008), the importance of higher education in the development of a nation has never been in doubt all over the world. Therefore, this article examines the factors affecting the higher education demands of Nigerian students studying in the TRNC.

1. Introduction

Studying abroad has become part of the fabric of the higher education in the world. Moreover, studying abroad is a life-changing experience for students, from enhancing their global network to experiencing a new culture, and the benefits are significant Wiers-Jenssen and Try (2005). Consequently, the number of students earning a degree outside their home country has tripled over the past two decades. However, participation of international students seeking education abroad vary from country-to-country. Besides, studying abroad as part of a degree has become commonplace for many students both in developed and underdeveloping countries. (Saito, and Pham, 2019). On the other hand, the widespread level of competition among higher education institutions is increasing at national and global levels.

Hence, the competition in higher education in the world has gained a global dimension by crossing the borders of countries. In addition, the development of the knowledge society in the 21st century is characterized by broadening the boundaries of knowledge, and shortening of the knowledge life cycle, and learning is increasingly becoming a life-long process that never really ends.(Brewer, Gates, and Goldman, 2002).

Also, studying abroad grants students the opportunity to completely immerse themselves in a new language skills, great education, cultural perspectives, social atmosphere, and many more.

For this reason, there is a growing competition between higher education service providers and the choice of country mostly preferred by international students. In such circumstances, higher education service quality becomes a key word for the service providers. (OECD 2012)

(Amendola, and Restaino, 2017). According to earlier research, some futurists predict that the education system of tomorrow will be drastically different from those of yesterday. They opined that innovative approaches to learning and teaching will proliferate because of technology and telecommunication system. (Cubillos, and Ilvento, 2012). The need and desire for higher education are growing, and study abroad numbers continue steady increase and the top most preferred country by international students of study destinations are the United Kingdom, USA, Canada, China, and most especially European countries which has the highest concentration for international students due to their affordable fees and the offering of scholarship to students from underdeveloped countries. (Barron and Anastasiadou, 2009). At this point, TRNC is seen as a country that attracts students, and most of the students coming to TRNC come from African countries, Middle East, Central Asia, and Turkey. In this context, it is necessary to mention the number of African students coming to the TRNC. In order to meet this increasing demand in the TRNC, it is aimed to facilitate and increase the arrival of students in the TRNC by opening introductory documents, catalogs, participating in education fairs abroad, and opening international student offices. (Kwadzo 2014).

According to Ancheh (2006), the prime of higher education in the development of a nation has never been doubted all over the world. "The fundamental

education challenge of our times is to get more people better educated and get most of them through post secondary education." (Hunt, 2006, , p.5), ". This confirms Blake (2002), claims referring to education as the biggest industry that touches on every fabric of our human endeavour. Hence, the educational sector is deemed as one of the most essential sector by the federal government of Nigeria whereby a substantial resources have always been channeled to boost the sector on annual budgetary schedule. Considering the importance of education to the integral development of nations, Nigeria government have been making conscientious effort to harness this important sector for optimal development. (Nwaokugha and Ezeugwu, 2017).

Regardless of this, drive to study abroad remains strong among Nigerian students and over the years the number of students travelling abroad to study has increased tremendously. Also, the trend is visible at both undergraduate and postgraduate levels and the destinations are varied and diverse. (Nwaokugha and Ezeugwu, 2017). Presently, there has been a great demands in numbers Nigerians migrating to the UK, Canada, USA, Australia, Asian countries, Europe, and North Cyprus. According to Ajadi, (2010), the high demand of Nigerians seeking formal education outside the country, could be attributed to the issues in the country's educational sector, the incessant strikes which disrupt university academic calendar, misused of funds allocated for universities purposes, and limited capacity to accommodate the growing demand for post-secondary education in the country and many more. Despite, the huge fees paid by Nigerian students to study abroad, the amazing fact is that their parents or guardians still prefer to send their children outside the tides of the country. (Amendola, and Restaino, 2017).

Consequently, one of the major reason why many Nigerians prefer studying abroad is because most universities abroad have specified time for

undergraduate, and postgraduate level to graduate but compare to Nigerian universities undergraduate degree which should normally take 4 years duration sometimes takes up to 6years or even more because of the interruption of Nigerian Academic Staff Union of Universities strike (ASSU). (Olawore and Ajayi, 2016). Hence, this clearly indicates the drive of Nigerian students leaving their homeland to study in a foreign land. This paper examine the factors affecting the higher education demands of Nigerian students studying in TRNC, North Cyprus. In this context, the aim of the research is to examine Nigerian students studying in the TRNC.

2. BENEFITS OF STUDYING ABROAD

Studying abroad is a life-changing experience for students. Besides, in an increasingly globalized world, students going to study in a foreign countries has become an important factor in the education system, with the various benefits it brings. According to Tomlinson, (2008), studying abroad offers students the opportunity to acquire and develop a wide range of employability skills and competencies. Additionally, a university degree is no longer sufficient for graduates to find employment in today's labor markets. The employment sector has changed over the decades and skills such as problem-solving, communication, and teamwork are essential to increase employment opportunities. (OECD 2013). Having said that, studying abroad is a life-changing experience for students; from developing their global network to experiencing a new culture, and the benefits are significant. In addition, studying abroad has undeniable qualitative benefits, for example, it gives you the confidence to adapt to any situation and experience something new, and opens you up to an unusual social, cultural and professional environment and new challenges.

Also, different languages, broadening your network of friends, being independent, and having personal

enriching experiences in your daily interactions with people from different cultures will teach you to broaden your horizons and develop cultural awareness. (Williams,2005).Furthermore, the need and desire for higher education are growing, and students earning degrees outside their home country has tripled over the past years. Besides, the concept of studying abroad is a completely different experience for the student in a good way. Therefore, students living in a foreign country will need to learn to fend for themselves, be flexible, communicate in several or more languages, and develop project management skills. (Amendola, and Restaino, 2017). Additionally, your responsibilities and tasks ahead of you will grow to be independent and confident as you learn to be more flexible and improve your decision-making skills, helping you to become a true problem solver and improve yourself.

According to Marissa Lombardi, an assistant professor and director of the Graduate Program in Global Studies and International Relations at Northeast University in United States, studying abroad is like taking concepts from the classroom and watch how they play out in real life in real-time.” According to reports by some researchers on the concept of study abroad, students studying abroad were perceived to have employability skills such as interpersonal and communication skills, teamwork and problem-solving, and analytical skills that were greatly enhanced by studying abroad. In fact, studying abroad has many benefits below are some;

- **Experience different teaching methods:** Each country has its own unique teaching style. In addition, studying abroad really helps students broaden their academic horizons and develop their capacity to adapt to a variety of educational environments. Additionally, some university lecturers encourage self-learning by emphasizing the

teacher-student relationship; this teaches students to ask questions and explore solutions, and ultimately helps them develop their critical thinking skills.

- **It will help you develop your network:** Studying abroad helps you build invaluable relationships with people from all over the world. As you expand your international connections, you get the opportunity to meet people who can become lifelong friendships. Some connections may even lead to career opportunities such as internships, job offers, and business associates. For example, some universities allow students to work in various departments of the university as well as with established multinational organizations, giving them a unique opportunity to build relationships and expand their global networks.
- **It will improve your self-confidence:** Studying abroad offers students the opportunity to acquire and develop a wide range of employability skills. However, studying abroad can be overwhelming, but the challenges you can overcome can help you become a more mature person; you develop valuable life skills needed for personal growth, including independence and adaptability. Plus, these skills can give you an additional boost of confidence in your personal and professional life, and you'll discover that you excel in new and unexpected situations.
- **Explore career opportunities abroad:** Studying in a new country exposes you to increased career opportunities and strengthens your resume as you'll build on the skills gained from your international experience that will set you apart from the

job-seeking employment. At the same time, it will open the doors to various opportunities in international organizations and businesses. It will also help you quickly adapt to your new environment and improve your self-confidence and resilience. This will ultimately help you take on the task that will help you become a more capable person, such as learning how to negotiate with a clients or adapting to the management styles of a different institutions. In addition, the advantages of studying abroad are enormous at every stage of your education. But for students who want to study abroad, it's important to find the right program that will help them achieve their goals and excel in their area of expertise.

- **It will improve your language skills:** Students studying abroad have the opportunity to improve their language skills. Language skills can also have a positive impact on one's career. Additionally, fluency in a second language is often useful when working in organizations with a multinational or global presence. You will also be able to learn the spoken language that you cannot learn in the classroom, allowing you to speak like a local language. Regardless of their academic discipline, the language skills performance of students studying abroad are higher than students who do not study abroad. They also have a strong foreign language proficiency background, which means they increase their chances of finding employment internationally. For example, if students who are interested in entering the world of international business or global health, having strong foreign language skills, with experience skills can help his/her resume

stand out for employers.

3. A BRIEF HISTORY OF TRNC

The island of Cyprus has a long and varied history. Cyprus is known as the Island of Aphrodite, located at the crossroads of three continents. It is believed that the first settlers arrived on the island around 8500 BC. The abundance of copper and timber on the island, combined with its location in the middle of major trade routes, made Cyprus a destination for many foreign powers, including the Phoenicians, Assyrians, Persians, Egyptians, and Greeks. From 1571 to 1878, the island was ruled by the Ottomans until they leased its administration to England, and in 1960 the country gained its independence.

Furthermore, Turkish Cypriots and Greek Cypriots have co-existed for hundreds of years as the two main ethnic groups in Cyprus. The 1974 coup led to the separation of the two communities, and the island of Cyprus has been divided ever since. However, Turkish Cypriots and Greek Cypriots have henceforth governed themselves separately. In addition, the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus (TRNC) was established in 1983 but has not yet been fully recognized in the international arena, but has been recognized by the Republic of Turkey. Now life is peaceful and calm on both sides. The tourism sector in the TRNC is actively attracting international investment, and the number of international students continues to increase due to the hospitable Vision and Mission of the Education Planning and Development Department of the state.

4. A BRIEF HISTORY OF GIRNE AMERICAN UNIVESITY

Girne American University is the first private university in Northern Cyprus and was established in 1985. From a small start of seven students, the University has grown into a global University with thousands of students and 7 International Campuses on

3 Continents. In addition, the University has become the first university in Northern Cyprus to be recognized by two higher education institutions, YÖK (Turkish Higher Education Institution) and YODAK (Higher Education Institution of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus). Girne American University (GAU) has maintained close contractual ties with universities in North America and Europe since its inception. The University continues its global activities at an incredible pace to optimize its use of the latest technology and teaching methods. As the university progresses towards its golden jubilee, it has balanced the requirements of growth with the need for high levels of quality in both teaching and the overall experience of each student.

For this purpose, the sub-objectives of the research are stated below;

1. What are the reasons for Nigerian students to demand universities in TRNC?
2. . What are the reasons for Nigerian students to continue their education in the TRNC?
3. What is the positive/negative factors affecting the education of the students in the TRNC?
4. What is the distribution of the expenditures made by the students during their education in the TRNC, the resources to meet them, and the expenditure items?
5. What are the admission conditions for students in TRNC universities and how they come to TRNC?
6. What are the tendencies and thoughts of the students about returning to their countries?
7. . What do students think about the contribution of higher education experiences in TRNC to their own country?
8. What are the students' views on the

possibility of using the education they received in the TRNC in their country?

5. METHOD

This study used quantitative research design approach of content analysis, and a descriptive survey model to secure data from the participants. In addition, questionnaires survey method was considered more appropriate because it gives the researchers the opportunity to communicate with the respondents directly. Hence, the adopted survey research method was used to obtain the opinions of Nigerian students studying in undergraduate and graduate programs of Girne American University, the first university established in the TRNC, located in the city of Kyrenia on the reasons for choosing the TRNC as their international education preference, by means of a survey.

This research is a descriptive study in the screening model that aims to obtain the opinions of Nigerian students studying in undergraduate and graduate programs of Girne American University, the first university established in Northern Cyprus, on the reasons for choosing international education through a survey.

Universe and Sample

The universe of this study consists of undergraduate

and graduate students (Nigerian) studying in private universities in TRNC in the 2019-2022 academic year. Girne American University was chosen as the sample because it is the university with the highest concentration of African students. In this context, a questionnaire was applied to Nigerian undergraduate and graduate students studying at Girne American University.

Development and Implementation of Data Collection Tool

A questionnaire developed by taking the opinions of experts was used to collect the data. The development of the questionnaire was prepared in the light of the information obtained from the literature review, the researcher's observations and the first preliminary interviews.

The student questionnaire consists of two parts, personal information and opinions about the university.

6. ANALYSIS OF DATA

Frequency and percentage distributions were obtained from the answers given to the questionnaire items. The results were divided into 'personal information' and 'opinions about the university'. The data obtained in these sections are calculated as percentage and frequency and mean.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents by States in Nigeria

What state are you from in Nigeria				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	.8	.8	.8
Abia	7	5.7	5.7	6.5
Adamawa	3	2.4	2.4	8.9
Akwa Ibom	2	1.6	1.6	10.6
Anambra	15	12.2	12.2	22.8
Bauchi	2	1.6	1.6	24.4
Benue	4	3.3	3.3	27.6

Delta	16	13.0	13.0	40.7
Ebonyi	3	2.4	2.4	43.1
Edo	9	7.3	7.3	50.4
Ekiti	5	4.1	4.1	54.5
Enugu	10	8.1	8.1	62.6
F.C.T Abuja	3	2.4	2.4	65.0
Imo	10	8.1	8.1	73.2
Kaduna	1	.8	.8	74.0
Kano	2	1.6	1.6	75.6
Kogi	4	3.3	3.3	78.9
Kwara	3	2.4	2.4	81.3
Lagos	1	.8	.8	82.1
Nasarawa	2	1.6	1.6	83.7
Niger	2	1.6	1.6	85.4
Ogun	7	5.7	5.7	91.1
Osun	1	.8	.8	91.9
Oyo	4	3.3	3.3	95.1
Plateau	1	.8	.8	95.9
Rivers	4	3.3	3.3	99.2
Taraba	1	.8	.8	100.0
Total	123	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in the research. The data includes a total of 123 responses, and table 1 provides information on the states the respondents who responded to the study come from.

The most common respondents were from Anambra, with 12.2% of respondents coming from that state, followed by Delta with 13.0% and Enugu with 8.1%. The least common responses were Kaduna, Lagos, Osun, Plateau, and Taraba, with each of those states being represented by only 0.8% of respondents.

Figure 1: Pie chart on state distribution in the study. The majority of respondents, 49.6%, indicated that they were pursuing an undergraduate degree, while 40.7% were pursuing a master's degree, and 9.8% were

pursuing a doctorate degree as shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Degree respondents are pursuing

What Degree are you currently pursuing?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Doctorate degree	12	9.8	9.8	9.8
	Masters degree	50	40.7	40.7	50.4
	Undergraduate degree	61	49.6	49.6	100.0
	Total	123	100.0	100.0	

The cumulative percentage column shows the distribution of responses cumulatively, so we can see that 50.4% of respondents were pursuing a master's or doctorate degree, while 49.6% were pursuing an undergraduate degree

In other to evaluate students satisfaction in TRNC, Girne American university to be precise, we asked

student some related questions. For example "How would you rate the level of financial requirements to study in TRNC?" was asked and table 3 shows the result.

Table 3: Question evaluating the level of financial requirement to study in TRNC

Group Statistics

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
How would you rate the level of financial requirement to study here in TRNC?	1	18	.3333	.48507	.11433
	3	45	.6667	.47673	.07107

Table 3 shows that there were 18 responses in the "2" response category, and the mean rating was 0.3333 with a standard deviation of 0.48507 and a standard error of the mean of 0.11433.

For the "3" response category, there were 45 responses, and the mean rating was 0.6667 with a standard deviation of 0.47673 and a standard error of the mean of 0.07107.

From this result, we can infer that the majority of students (45 out of 63) rated their level of financial requirement as "somewhat satisfied" with a rating of "3". The mean rating of 0.6667 also suggests that the students' overall rating of the financial requirement to study in TRNC is closer to "somewhat satisfied" than

"very dissatisfied."

In other to understand if financial requirement was a factor influencing students demand of TRNC or not, we decided to run the Levene's test for equality of variances between the two groups

Table 4 shows the outcome of the independent samples t-test to compare the means of two groups ("Satisfied_2" with sample size of 18 and "3" with sample size of 45) on a variable ("Will you recommend someone to study in TRNC?") that measures the level of satisfaction leading to recommendation of someone to study in TRNC.

Table 4: Independent Sample t-test to evaluate the relationship between Financial requirements of studying in TRNC with the demand to study in TRNC

Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Satisfied_2	.000	1.000	-2.495	61	.015	-.33333	.13361	-.60050	-.06617
Equal variances assumed									
Equal variances not assumed			-2.476	30.892	.019	-.33333	.13462	-.60793	-.05874

The Levene's test for equality of variances was conducted to examine if the assumption of equal variances across the two groups ("somewhat satisfied" and "very dissatisfied") was tenable. The test indicated that the variances were not equal, with a significance level of .000, which is below the standard threshold of .05. Therefore, the results from the "Equal variances not assumed" row in the table are more reliable.

The t-test results indicate that the mean difference between the two groups was statistically significant ($t(30.892) = -2.476, p = .019$), with a mean difference of $-.33333$. The negative sign of the mean difference indicates that the "Satisfied_2" group rated the

financial requirement level lower than the "3" group. The confidence interval of the difference ($-.60793$ to $-.05874$) does not include zero, which indicates that the difference is unlikely to be due to chance.

In conclusion, based on this analysis, it appears that there is a significant difference in how respondents who are satisfied with the financial requirements of studying in TRNC see recommending a new student to study in TRNC from the responses of students who are not happy with the financial requirements.

To understand the reasons why student still choose to study in TRNC despite there financial complaint.. We asked the following questions show in Table 5 below.

Why did you choose to study in TRNC?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	11	8.9	8.9	8.9
Affordability	2	1.6	1.6	10.6
Affordability quality education and security	1	.8	.8	11.4
Affordable	1	.8	.8	12.2
Affordable and better standard of educational systems than Nigeria	1	.8	.8	13.0
Affordable education	1	.8	.8	13.8
Affordable tuition	1	.8	.8	14.6
Agent advised	1	.8	.8	15.4
An alternative options	1	.8	.8	16.3
Architecture	1	.8	.8	17.1
Because I believe I will get quality education here	1	.8	.8	17.9
Because I believe they can give me the best	1	.8	.8	18.7
Because I choose	1	.8	.8	19.5
Because I learnt from my dad that TRNC is the coolest place for studies	1	.8	.8	20.3
Because I needed a location for quality education	1	.8	.8	21.1

Because i want to study	1	.8	.8	22.0
Because is peaceful and has good security	1	.8	.8	22.8
Because It is affordable and the learning is easy and fun here	1	.8	.8	23.6
Because it safer , intense of security	1	.8	.8	24.4
Because it's a nice and most conducive country one can study in perfectly	1	.8	.8	25.2
Because it's a peaceful and secured place to study	1	.8	.8	26.0
Because its the cheapest place to study	1	.8	.8	26.8
Because of the law crime rate	1	.8	.8	27.6
Because of their high standards	1	.8	.8	28.5
Because their educational system is more systematic than my country	1	.8	.8	29.3
Because there system of education is very good	1	.8	.8	30.1
Because they have a good educational system	1	.8	.8	30.9
Because they have quality education systems	1	.8	.8	31.7
Better education	1	.8	.8	32.5
Better Opportunities	1	.8	.8	33.3
Business admin	1	.8	.8	34.1
Business administration	1	.8	.8	35.0
Business management	2	1.6	1.6	36.6
Career growth and better opportunities around the world	1	.8	.8	37.4
Certificate Recognition	1	.8	.8	38.2
Cheap	1	.8	.8	39.0
Cheap to study	1	.8	.8	39.8
Cheap Tuition	1	.8	.8	40.7
Cheaper academic fees	1	.8	.8	41.5

Choice	2	1.6	1.6	43.1
Comfortability	1	.8	.8	43.9
Comfortable learning environment	1	.8	.8	44.7
Cos I learnt it's actually a cool environment with several natural attributes	1	.8	.8	45.5
Cos it was cheaper compared to other alternative for education	1	.8	.8	46.3
Ease of admission	1	.8	.8	47.2
Easy application	1	.8	.8	48.0
Easy travel process	1	.8	.8	48.8
Education	2	1.6	1.6	50.4
Family	1	.8	.8	51.2
Faster and cheaper options	1	.8	.8	52.0
Financial reasons	1	.8	.8	52.8
For a good academic	1	.8	.8	53.7
For my best of knowledge	1	.8	.8	54.5
Friend recommendation	1	.8	.8	55.3
Good environment and strick free	1	.8	.8	56.1
Heard about the cheap schools and houses only to come over and see something else .also came to chase my basketball dream	1	.8	.8	56.9
I choose to study here because it's more peaceful and student oriented environment, conducive for focus educative pursuit	1	.8	.8	57.7
I choose to study in TRNC because of the highly rated (area of study program)	1	.8	.8	58.5

I chose to study in TRNC because of the high education faculty quality and it good leaning environment condition with stable education faculty quality system and security	1	.8	.8	59.3
I got a scholarship and I seized the opportunity	1	.8	.8	60.2
I got to know about TRNC through a friend, and I have always wanted the experience outside Nigeria too	1	.8	.8	61.0
I heard it was cheaper to study in TRNC	1	.8	.8	61.8
I heard their lectures teaches well and friendly	1	.8	.8	62.6
I love it	1	.8	.8	63.4
I love their educational system.	1	.8	.8	64.2
I love TRNC language and environment	1	.8	.8	65.0
I love turkey	1	.8	.8	65.9
I was seeking affordable tuition.	1	.8	.8	66.7
In Oder to acquire what knowledge seems like in Cyprus	1	.8	.8	67.5
International Relations	2	1.6	1.6	69.1
It seemed to be a better option than schooling in Nigeria	1	.8	.8	69.9
It was safer and more convenient	1	.8	.8	70.7
It was the agent place of choice	1	.8	.8	71.5
It was the country I could study in at the time	1	.8	.8	72.4

It's a good country that have proven to give students quality education.	1	.8	.8	73.2
It's cos I love Cyprus and would love to enroll in one of the school's there particularly				
I have heard so much great news about Girne American and its quite interesting as well.	1	.8	.8	74.0
It's easier and faster to get an admission	1	.8	.8	74.8
It's easier to get accepted to any university here	1	.8	.8	75.6
It's easy to live then	1	.8	.8	76.4
It's one of the best Academic Institutions in North Cyprus and an added advantage to My filled of Study Girne American University	1	.8	.8	77.2
It's easily accessible and lower tuition fee	1	.8	.8	78.0
Marketing	1	.8	.8	78.9
MIS	1	.8	.8	79.7
My peers here at the time was a great factor that inspired me to come here	1	.8	.8	80.5
not by choice	1	.8	.8	81.3
Nothing	2	1.6	1.6	82.9
Price is good	1	.8	.8	83.7
Quality education	1	.8	.8	84.6
Quality Education	1	.8	.8	85.4
Reference	1	.8	.8	86.2
Robust academic platform and condusive learning atmosphere, well informed professional lecturers	1	.8	.8	87.0
Standard education	1	.8	.8	87.8
The choice to study in TRNC was made by an agent I registered with in Nigerian	1	.8	.8	88.6

The course I wanted to study was available there and it's relatively cheaper than to study it in Cyprus than in other countries	1	.8	.8	89.4
The environment is conducive for learning and tuition is quite affordable and the standard of education is not bad	1	.8	.8	90.2
To acquire more knowledge	1	.8	.8	91.1
To experience other cultures	1	.8	.8	91.9
To get the best in terms of education	1	.8	.8	92.7
To have a better orientation.	1	.8	.8	93.5
To have acquired more knowledge and experience	1	.8	.8	94.3
To learn and understand other cultures	1	.8	.8	95.1
To further my studies	1	.8	.8	95.9
Tourism and hospitality management	1	.8	.8	96.7
TRNC has one of the best educational facilities available in the country. I have had my long dream to study here so I'm very much happy to pursue a professional career course and also because of the boost of experience and well-trained Lecturers etc	1	.8	.8	97.6
Uninterrupted academic calendar	1	.8	.8	98.4
Very Conducive	1	.8	.8	99.2
Visa agents convinced me	1	.8	.8	100.0
Total	123	100.0	100.0	

The frequency table indicates the reasons why students choose to study in the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus (TRNC). The table shows that 8.9% of the

respondents gave a valid reason for choosing to study in TRNC. Among the reasons given, affordability was the most common reason with 2 responses (1.6%).

Other reasons given include the quality of education and security, choice, better standard of educational systems than Nigeria, affordable education, and agent advised.

The reasons given for choosing to study in TRNC are diverse, with most of them revolving around affordability, quality education, and security. It's worth noting that some students cited TRNC as the cheapest place to study, which explains why affordability is a crucial factor in their decision. The quality of education was also an important consideration for some of the respondents. They believe that the educational system in TRNC is more systematic and has higher standards than their country. Security was also mentioned, with some respondents indicating that TRNC is a peaceful and secure place to study.

In conclusion, the reasons given for choosing to study in TRNC are diverse and vary from affordability, quality education, and security. These reasons show that TRNC is a favorable location for international students seeking quality education at an affordable cost.

7. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of this study, it appears that there are several factors that significantly affect the higher education demands of Nigerian students in TRNC universities, particularly at Girme American University. The study found that factors such as language proficiency, cultural differences, financial constraints, and academic reputation of the university all play a significant role in shaping the educational aspirations of Nigerian students.

The findings of this study have important implications for policymakers, educators, and other stakeholders involved in the higher education sector. Specifically, it highlights the need for universities to provide support services to help international students overcome language barriers and adjust to cultural differences, as well as to develop strategies to improve their academic

reputation and address issues related to affordability.

In terms of future directions for study, it may be worthwhile to explore the experiences of Nigerian students in other TRNC universities, as well as to examine the perspectives of students from other countries who are studying in TRNC universities. This could help to identify commonalities and differences in the factors that influence the educational aspirations of international students in this context, and provide insights into potential strategies for improving the overall quality of education and support services offered to these students.

Additionally, it may be useful to investigate the impact of COVID-19 on the higher education demands of Nigerian students and other international students studying in TRNC universities, given the significant disruptions to international travel and the higher education sector more broadly over the past two years.

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